

Deep Learning With Width-Wise Early Exiting and Rejection for Computational Efficient and Trustworthy Modulation Classification

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ABSTRACT The development of trustworthy and efficient Deep Learning (DL) models is vital for wireless communications, supporting tasks such as automatic modulation classification (AMC), spectrum use, and network optimization. Yet, deploying DL on resource-constrained edge devices remains challenging due to energy and reliability concerns. We propose a width-wise early exiting architecture, a variation of conventional early exiting that enables classification after processing only part of a signal frame. To further improve reliability, we introduce an *early rejection* mechanism, applying confidence-based abstention both at intermediate exits and the final output. In AMC experiments, our model achieves on average 40% less computation (up to 60% in some cases), while improving classification accuracy by 3% in low-SNR conditions. These results highlight the potential of our approach for robust, efficient, and trustworthy ML deployment in wireless environments.

INDEX TERMS Classification quality, computational efficiency, cross-entropy, deep learning, early exiting, early rejection, modulation classification, selective classification, trustworthy AI, wireless channel.

I. INTRODUCTION

AUTOMATIC Modulation Classification (AMC) plays a central role in modern wireless systems, supporting spectrum awareness, interference detection, dynamic spectrum access, and military surveillance [1]. In recent years, Deep Learning (DL)-based approaches have become dominant, achieving State-of-the-Art (SotA) performance under diverse channel conditions [2]. Architectures such as ResNet [3], MCNet [4], and Radio Transformers [5] automatically extract discriminative features from raw signal data, providing significant accuracy gains over traditional methods.

Despite these advances, current DL-based AMC solutions remain computationally intensive and energy demanding, limiting their deployment on edge devices with heterogeneous resources. At the same time, the increasing integration of AI into wireless networks raises the need for models that are not only efficient but also trustworthy and explainable [6]. Trustworthiness—defined by robustness, reli-

ability, and human interpretability—is especially critical in safety-sensitive tasks such as interference detection. However, optimizing efficiency and trustworthiness together is non-trivial, as methods that improve one often degrade the other.

Prior research has explored strategies to reduce the computational burden of DL models, including deployment on low-power hardware [7], spiking neural networks [8], model compression [9], and adaptive inference [10]. Among these, (Early Exiting (EE)) has shown particular promise, allowing confident samples to exit at shallow layers and reducing inference cost [11]. However, in convolutional neural networks (CNNs)-based architectures, where early convolutional layers dominate the compute budget, depth-based EE achieves only limited savings [12]. To address this limitation, we recently introduced Width-Wise Early Exiting (WWEE) [13], a model-agnostic technique designed to enhance the efficiency and performance of any CNN-based classifier. Unlike depth-based EE, WWEE adaptively widens the input

processed by the network, tailoring computation to input complexity.

Parallel to efficiency, selective classification (also known as classification with rejection) offers a means to enhance trustworthiness by abstaining from low-confidence predictions [14]. This approach has proven effective in domains such as healthcare [15], finance [16], and autonomous systems [17], but remains underexplored in wireless communications. In AMC, selective rejection can prevent unreliable predictions under challenging low-SNR conditions, improving system-level performance in distributed settings [18].

Taken together, these two directions reveal a gap: existing methods either improve efficiency (e.g., early exiting) or reliability (e.g., selective classification), but no prior work combines them within a unified framework for AMC. This motivates our contribution: we extend the WWEE architecture with selective classification mechanisms, enabling adaptive, resource-aware, and trustworthy inference for AMC in wireless networks.

To demonstrate our method's potential, we chose ResNet as our baseline for two key reasons. First, it is a foundational, widely adopted, and well-understood architecture in deep learning. Its foundational principles, such as residual connections, have influenced nearly all subsequent architectures, making it a highly relevant and reproducible benchmark. Second, by using a stable model like ResNet, we can isolate the specific benefits of our proposed WWEE technique, such as computational load reduction, without introducing confounding variables from a more recent or complex architecture. This focused approach provides a clear and unambiguous proof-of-concept for the WWEE method.

The main contributions of this work are:

- We extend the WWEE architecture with confidence-based early acceptance, allowing predictions on partial input data and reducing unnecessary computation.
- We introduce trustworthiness into DL-AMC by incorporating confidence-based rejection at the final exit and, for the first time, at intermediate exits (early rejection). This enables the model to proactively abstain from uncertain predictions, simultaneously improving decision quality and efficiency.
- We present a comprehensive evaluation against ResNet-based baselines, comparing models with and without rejection mechanisms. Results show that our approach reduces average computational cost by 40% while maintaining or improving classification quality.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the relevant literature. Section III formally defines the Automatic Modulation Classification (AMC) problem and details our proposed system architecture. Section IV describes selective classification in the context of a SotA ResNet-based model, while Section V introduces our novel WWEE architecture and its configurations. Section VI outlines the experimental methodology, including datasets, model design parameters, and evaluation metrics.

Section VII presents implementation details and thresholds for both WWEE and ResNet models. Section VIII discusses results on accuracy, coverage, efficiency, and prediction quality. Section IX summarizes the main findings, and Section X concludes with promising directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

This section first reviews modulation classification, the primary application of our work. We then discuss early exiting and selective classification, as these two concepts form the foundational basis for our proposed method.

A. MODULATION CLASSIFICATION

The goal of AMC is to identify the modulation scheme of an unknown radio signal without any prior information. Research on AMC has been ongoing for over four decades. Broadly, three distinct methodological streams can be identified: Likelihood-Based (LB) [19], Feature-Based (FB) [20], and DL [21]. DL-AMC in particular has gained lots of attention over recent years.

DL-AMC in particular has gained significant attention in recent years, as it relies on deep neural networks to automatically extract discriminative features from raw signal data. Its key advantages include end-to-end learning, which eliminates the need for manual feature engineering, and its remarkable classification accuracy even in complex, noisy, and variable channel conditions. While early works primarily used CNNs [22] and recurrent neural networks (Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)) [23], recent advancements have explored more sophisticated architectures to push the boundaries of performance. These include models leveraging attention mechanisms to improve feature extraction [24] and lightweight architectures such as MobileViT [25] and Radio Transformers [5] for resource-constrained environments.

Despite these advancements, the computational demands of these complex networks remain a notable challenge. A promising direction to mitigate this involves optimizing the inference process by allowing models to make predictions and exit early in their processing pipeline, leading to significant computational savings.

B. EARLY EXITING FOR COMPUTATIONAL EFFICIENCY

To improve the computational efficiency of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), EE has emerged as a promising adaptive inference technique. Its goal is to reduce inference time and computational cost while preserving model accuracy. Architectures such as BranchyNet [11] and multi-exit models [26] have shown that early exiting can effectively balance accuracy and efficiency.

A common strategy is confidence-based inference, where intermediate classifiers are placed at various network depths. The model exits early once the confidence of an intermediate classifier exceeds a predefined threshold [27]. This threshold controls the trade-off: exiting too early may prevent the model from leveraging deeper, more accurate representations,

while exiting too late reduces efficiency. Moreover, as noted in [28], models sometimes suffer from *overthinking*, where an initially correct prediction is overturned at a deeper layer, leading to a final misclassification.

In the context of AMC, [29] demonstrated the potential of EE to accelerate inference. However, a systematic exploration of early exiting for AMC efficiency is still lacking. Existing approaches have focused on depth-wise EE, whereas our recently proposed WWEE introduces a novel perspective. The motivation stems from two observations: (i) in CNNs, the early convolutional layers are typically the most computationally expensive [12]; and (ii) in modulation recognition, reliable classification often does not require processing the full input signal. WWEE addresses both issues by progressively widening the portion of the input that is processed, thereby adapting computation to the inherent complexity of the sample.

C. SELECTIVE CLASSIFICATION FOR TRUSTWORTHY INFERENCE

While early exiting improves efficiency, it does not inherently guarantee reliable predictions. In wireless communication systems, particularly for tasks such as AMC, unreliable predictions can lead to inefficient spectrum usage, increased interference, and reduced throughput in cognitive radio and dynamic spectrum access scenarios [30].

Selective classification addresses this challenge by allowing a model to abstain from classifying low-confidence instances [14]. In AMC, for example, predictions made under challenging low-Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) conditions may be rejected. By abstaining from these uncertain cases, the model achieves higher accuracy on the subset of predictions it does make. This introduces a trade-off between *coverage*, the proportion of classified samples, and *accuracy*, the reliability of those classifications.

The foundations of this trade-off were laid by Chow in the 1970s [31], and subsequent research has explored its integration into deep learning. Popular approaches include confidence-thresholding, where predictions are rejected below a probability threshold [32]; cost-sensitive learning, which minimizes an explicit misclassification–rejection cost [33]; and explicit rejector models, which train a secondary module to identify samples that should be abstained from [34]. Each approach balances coverage and accuracy differently, but confidence-based thresholding is attractive in practice due to its simplicity and fine-grained control.

D. PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

In this work, we adopt confidence-thresholding as the basis for rejection, leveraging the metrics proposed in [35] to determine optimal thresholds. To the best of our knowledge, this represents the first application of selective classification in the AMC domain, and the first integration of selective classification into a WWEE framework. By jointly exploiting confidence-based early rejection and width-wise early exit-

ing, our approach improves both computational efficiency and trustworthiness, yielding reliable performance within constrained computational budgets.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a wireless communication system in which a transmitter sends digitally modulated signals over a wireless channel. These signals are subsequently received by a given receiver that aims to classify the modulation used in the signal from a class of known modulations, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The set of modulation schemes considered in this work is:

$$\mathcal{M} = \{\text{BPSK}, \text{QPSK}, \text{8-PSK}, \text{4-PAM}, \text{16-QAM}, \text{64-QAM}\},$$

which spans a range from simple binary modulation to more complex higher-order schemes. We consider a wireless channel modeled as flat fading with Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN). This simplified channel model isolates the effect of SNR on classification performance, allowing a precise evaluation of the robustness of the proposed models under varying noise conditions.

At the receiver, the Radio Frequency (RF) signal is down-converted to the baseband, digitized by an analog-to-digital converter, and represented as a sequence of complex In-phase/Quadrature (IQ) samples: $z[n] = I[n] + jQ[n]$. These samples preserve the amplitude and phase information of the received signal.

Our AMC models use frames of 512 consecutive IQ samples for both training and inference. This frame size provides an adequate representation for high-order modulations like 64-QAM. As Fig. 2 shows, we selected this input size because it offers a good balance between computational load and accuracy.

The goal of the proposed AMC model is to classify modulation types while balancing accuracy and computational cost. To achieve this, we adopt a multi-exit architecture that allows for early classification or rejection at intermediate points in the network, as conceptually illustrated in Fig. 1. It is important to note that the individual submodels depicted in Fig. 1 do not necessarily represent distinct, isolated components of the proposed network. Instead, the figure primarily illustrates the submodel from an exit point of view, clarifying which input segments contribute to the prediction at each specific exit. In this architecture, decisions are refined by progressively incorporating more input information. The first exit processes an initial segment of the IQ frame. If a prediction is deferred, subsequent exits incorporate new, additional segments of the input and also incorporate features derived from preceding branches. This allows the model to make early decisions based on minimal initial computation, and to refine its judgment with additional data only when needed, ultimately utilizing the full frame at the final exit.

At each exit, the model may accept a confident prediction, reject uncertain samples, or defer to a wider branch. Exiting early leads to computational savings, as wider branches are only triggered when necessary. Samples with high SNR

FIGURE 1. System model for the proposed automatic modulation classification in wireless communications.

FIGURE 2. Trade off between computational load and accuracy for different input sizes.

or lower-order modulation are typically easier to classify and are often accepted at earlier exits. More ambiguous or noisy samples may require deeper analysis or be rejected entirely to avoid incorrect predictions. Incorporating rejection improves trustworthiness by allowing the model to abstain from low-confidence decisions. The main challenge lies in jointly optimizing the confidence thresholds at each exit to balance accuracy, coverage, and computational cost. This selective classification mechanism, combined with early exiting, ensures that each sample is processed with just the necessary amount of computation, enhancing both efficiency and overall reliability. This selective classification mechanism is introduced in the following section.

IV. SELECTIVE RESNET MODEL ARCHITECTURE

This section details the implementation of selective classification in a ResNet model, originally proposed by O’Shea et al. [3] for modulation classification of raw IQ samples. We adapt this architecture by introducing a rejection mechanism, which we refer to as ResNet with Rejection (ResNet+R). ResNet+R incorporates a confidence threshold at its final exit layer, enabling the model to decide whether to make a prediction or abstain.

FIGURE 3. Architecture of the selective ResNet model with confidence-based rejection.

We chose ResNet as our baseline because it is a foundational, widely adopted, and well-understood architecture in DL. Using a stable and reproducible model like ResNet allows us to isolate the benefits of our proposed WVEE, such as computational load reduction, without introducing confounding variables from a more recent or complex architectures.

A. RESNET+R MODEL ARCHITECTURE

The ResNet+R architecture, based on the conventional ResNet-architecture [36] shown in Fig. 3, is designed for classification and selectively rejects low-confidence predictions. It consists of four residual stacks for feature extraction and three fully connected layers for classification. The model is functionally divided into four key blocks: the input, feature extractor, decision, and exit blocks.

The input block prepares incoming N IQ samples by arranging them into an $N \times 2$ matrix, where N is a tunable hyperparameter that influences computational complexity. The feature extractor block employs four residual stacks to learn complex representations. Each stack consists of two residual units with 32 filters of size (1,3) and a max-pooling layer for downsampling. The decision block flattens the extracted features and processes them through three fully connected layers. The first two dense layers have 128 neurons and use the SeLU activation function, while the final layer employs a softmax activation to produce a probability distribution over the C modulation classes. Unlike the conventional

ResNet, the ResNet+R model includes an exit block that implements a confidence-based rejection mechanism. This mechanism uses the normalized entropy of the output probability vector as a measure of uncertainty. Normalized entropy, calculated as

$$H(\hat{\mathbf{y}}) = -\frac{1}{\log_2 \mathcal{C}} \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{C}} \hat{y}_i \log_2 \hat{y}_i, \quad (1)$$

is in the range $[0, 1]$, with lower values indicating higher certainty. At inference time, the model accepts a prediction only if its entropy is below a predefined rejection threshold $\tau_{\text{reject, final}}$. This selective rejection prioritizes the reliability of accepted classifications by abstaining from predictions when uncertainty is high.

B. RESNET+R MODEL TRAINING AND INFERENCE PROCEDURE

The training of the ResNet+R model involves two primary objectives: learning the optimal weights for the network's layers and determining an appropriate rejection threshold $\tau_{\text{reject, final}}$ for reliable inference. The network weights were learned using standard supervised learning techniques. Specifically, we trained the model using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $5e-5$ over 40 epochs, implementing early stopping based on validation data, minimizing the categorical cross-entropy loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}, \mathbf{y}) = -\sum_{i=0}^{\mathcal{C}} y_i \log(\hat{y}_i), \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ represents the probability vector and \mathbf{y} represents the one-hot encoded true label. When the true label is one-hot encoded, such that $y_c = 1$ for the correct class c and $y_i = 0$ for all $i \neq c$, this loss function simplifies to

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}, \mathbf{y}) = -\log(\hat{y}_c). \quad (3)$$

Once the model weights are trained, the optimal rejection threshold $\tau_{\text{reject, final}}$ is determined by evaluating the model's predictions on the training data and maximizing the classification quality, following the methodology proposed in [35]. This process involves categorizing the predictions based on whether the prediction is correct or incorrect, and whether the prediction is accepted or rejected based on a given threshold τ . The classification quality $Q(\tau)$ for a given threshold τ is then defined based on the counts of these outcomes:

$$Q(\tau) = \frac{C_{CR}(\tau) + C_{CA}(\tau)}{C_{CA}(\tau) + C_{CR}(\tau) + C_{WA}(\tau) + C_{WR}(\tau)}. \quad (4)$$

where:

- $C_{CA}(\tau)$ denotes the count of Correctly Accepted predictions, where the model correctly identified the modulation and the prediction's confidence was above the acceptance threshold τ .
- $C_{WA}(\tau)$ denotes the count of Wrongly Accepted predictions, where the model incorrectly identified the

modulation, but the prediction's confidence was still above the acceptance threshold τ .

- $C_{CR}(\tau)$ denotes the count of Correctly Rejected predictions, where the model incorrectly identified the modulation, and the prediction's confidence was below the acceptance threshold τ , leading to rejection.
- $C_{WR}(\tau)$ denotes the count of Wrongly Rejected predictions, where the model correctly identified the modulation, but the prediction's confidence was below the acceptance threshold τ , leading to unnecessary rejection.

The optimal rejection threshold $\tau_{\text{reject, final}}$ is determined by maximizing this classification quality:

$$\tau_{\text{reject, final}} = \arg \max_{\tau} Q(\tau). \quad (5)$$

This optimal threshold ensures a desirable balance between accepting high-confidence, likely correct predictions and rejecting low-confidence, potentially incorrect ones, thereby enhancing the robustness of the inference process. It is important to note that the confidence values are based on normalized entropies, typically ranging from 0 to 1. Consequently, if $\tau_{\text{reject, final}}$ is chosen to be greater than 1 (i.e., outside the range of normalized entropies), the model will effectively not yield any rejections. In this specific scenario, the classification quality $Q(\tau)$ will become equivalent to the standard classification accuracy, and all predictions will be accepted.

Having trained the model and determined $\tau_{\text{reject, final}}$, we now describe how inference proceeds at test time. During inference, the ResNet+R model employs the determined optimal threshold $\tau_{\text{reject, final}}$ to decide on the final output. For a given input sample, the model first produces a probability distribution $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ over the modulation classes. The normalized entropy $H(\hat{\mathbf{y}})$ of this distribution is then calculated using (1). The final prediction \hat{m} is determined as follows:

$$\hat{m} = \begin{cases} \arg \max(\hat{\mathbf{y}}) & \text{if } H(\hat{\mathbf{y}}) < \tau_{\text{reject, final}} \\ \text{Reject Prediction} & \text{if } H(\hat{\mathbf{y}}) \geq \tau_{\text{reject, final}} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Thus, the threshold $\tau_{\text{reject, final}}$ governs the trade-off between the model's confidence and the decision to refrain from making predictions in ambiguous cases, such as when multiple modulation types have similar high probabilities, thereby reducing the risk of misclassification and enhancing the reliability of the system.

V. WIDTH-WISE EARLY EXITING ARCHITECTURE

This section introduces our proposed WVEE architecture, a novel approach designed to enhance the computational efficiency of AMC on resource-constrained devices. To further increase trustworthiness, we extend the base WVEE architecture with selective classification. We detail two distinct implementations of selective classification within this framework: WVEE+R, where the rejection mechanism is applied solely at the final exit point of the model, and WVEE+ER,

FIGURE 4. Proposed WWEE model with three sequential branches, illustrating the feature concatenation mechanism. The used parameters are summarised in table 1.

which extends this rejection capability to all intermediate exits.

A. WWEE MODEL ARCHITECTURE

The proposed WWEE architecture, illustrated in Fig. 4, processes the input signal through three parallel branches. A splitting layer dictates the number of IQ samples corresponding to each branch, dividing the original N samples into progressively increasing segments: N_0 , N_1 , and N_2 . Although the branches are structured in parallel from an architectural perspective, they are evaluated sequentially during inference, with potential early exits at each stage. The initial, narrower branch performs an initial feature extraction and classification attempt. Based on the confidence of this prediction, determined by dynamically learned acceptance and rejection criteria detailed in Subsection V-B, the processing can take one of three paths: termination with a confident early classification (leading to computational savings), early rejection due to low confidence (avoiding unnecessary deeper computations), or deferring to the subsequent, wider branch. In the latter case, the features extracted by each branch are cumulatively concatenated with those from all preceding branches.

Each branch in the WWEE architecture is structured with a feature extraction block (identical to the ResNet’s residual stacks), a decision block (fully connected layers mirroring the ResNet+R), and an exit block. A difference from the ResNet+R is the introduction of a concatenation layer before the decision block in all branches except the first. This concatenation layer fuses the feature maps from all preceding branches with the features of the current branch, enabling the subsequent layers to leverage the increasingly rich representations learned across different network widths. The sequential widening and processing continue until a confident

Algorithm 1 WWEE Training

Require: \mathcal{D} Training Dataset,
 θ_{init} randomly initialized model parameters,
Ensure: θ trained weights of the model,
 $\tau_{accept,0\dots N_e-2}$ acceptance thresholds,
 $\tau_{reject,0\dots N_e-1}$ rejection thresholds

- 1: **1. Joint Training Phase**
- 2: $\theta_{joint} \leftarrow \text{Train}(\theta_{init}, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{L}_{joint})$
- 3: **2. Expert-specific Fine-tuning**
- 4: $\mathcal{D}_0 \leftarrow \mathcal{D}$ \triangleright Initialize dataset for expert training
- 5: $[\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_{N_e-1}] \leftarrow \theta_{joint}$ \triangleright Split model into branches
- 6: **for** $e = 0$ to $N_e - 1$ **do**
- 7: $\theta_e \leftarrow \text{Train}(\theta_e, \mathcal{D}_e, \mathcal{L})$
- 8: $\text{Freeze}(\theta_e)$ \triangleright Prevent further updates
- 9: **if** $e == N_e - 1$ **then**
- 10: $\tau_{reject,N_e-1} \leftarrow \arg \max_{\tau} Q_{\mathcal{D}_e}(\tau)$
- 11: $\mathcal{D}_{reject,final} \leftarrow \text{splitDataset}(\mathcal{D}_e, \tau_{reject,N_e-1})$
- 12: **else**
- 13: $\tau_{accept,e} \leftarrow \text{acceptanceThreshold}(\theta_e, \mathcal{D}_e)$
- 14: $\mathcal{D}_{e+1}, \mathcal{D}_{accept,e} \leftarrow \text{splitDataset}(\mathcal{D}_e, \tau_{accept,e})$
- 15: **end if**
- 16: **end for**
- 17: $\theta \leftarrow [\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_{N_e-1}]$
- 18: **3. Early Reject Criteria**
- 19: $\mathcal{D}_{reject,0} \leftarrow \mathcal{D}_{reject,final}$
- 20: **for** $e = 0$ to $N_e - 2$ **do**
- 21: $\tau_{reject,e} \leftarrow \arg \max_{\tau} Q_{\mathcal{D}_{reject,e}}(\tau)$
- 22: $\mathcal{D}_{reject,e+1}, \mathcal{D}_{rejected} \leftarrow \text{splitDataset}(\mathcal{D}_{reject,e}, \tau_{reject,e})$ \leftarrow
- 23: **end for**

prediction is made, or the sample is rejected due to low confidence. Even upon reaching the final, full-width branch, the model might abstain from making a prediction if the confidence remains insufficient. The exit block at each branch acts as an intermediate classifier operating on the features available up to that point. The final exit block functions similarly to the ResNet+R’s exit, using an entropy-based acceptance threshold. However, the intermediate exit blocks are more sophisticated, employing both acceptance and rejection thresholds. These thresholds allow the model to not only confidently accept early predictions but also to proactively reject uncertain samples, preventing unnecessary computation in deeper branches.

B. WWEE MODEL TRAINING PROCEDURE

The WWEE model undergoes a carefully orchestrated three-stage training process to optimize both the classification accuracy at each exit and the effectiveness of the early exit criteria. These stages are joint training, expert-specific fine-tuning, and rejection threshold determination, as detailed in Algorithm 1.

1) JOINT TRAINING

Initially, the entire WWEE network is trained end-to-end using a joint loss function \mathcal{L}_{joint} defined as an equally weighted sum of the categorical cross-entropy losses computed at each exit point. For each exit e , the network produces a corresponding probability vector $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_e$. This loss function can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{L}_{joint}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}, \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{e=0}^{N_e-1} \mathcal{L}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}_e, \mathbf{y}), \quad (7)$$

where N_e is the number of exits. This joint training aims to learn a shared feature representation beneficial across all branches and early exit points. Specifically, we trained the model using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $1e-4$ over 40 epochs, implementing early stopping based on the validation dataset.

2) EXPERT-SPECIFIC FINE-TUNING

At the end of the expert-specific fine-tuning stage, two outcomes are produced. First, each classifier corresponding to an exit is retrained on a progressively more specialized subset of the training data. Second, a set of entropy-based thresholds is derived: acceptance thresholds $\tau_{\text{accept},e}$ for each intermediate exit ($e = 0, \dots, N_e - 2$), and a rejection threshold $\tau_{\text{reject},N_e-1}$ for the final exit. These thresholds are used during training for data partitioning and during inference to determine whether a sample should be accepted or passed to the next exit. The fine-tuning procedure begins with the first exit classifier, which is retrained on the training dataset \mathcal{D}_0 . After training, an acceptance threshold $\tau_{\text{accept},0}$ is computed to select the samples accepted at this exit, forming $\mathcal{D}_{\text{accept},0}$, while the remaining samples are deferred to the next exit, becoming \mathcal{D}_1 . This process is iteratively repeated for each subsequent classifier, with classifier e being retrained on the subset \mathcal{D}_e . A new threshold $\tau_{\text{accept},e}$ is then calculated to define $\mathcal{D}_{\text{accept},e}$, the samples accepted at exit e , and those moving on to $\mathcal{D}_{e+1} = \mathcal{D}_e \setminus \mathcal{D}_{\text{accept},e}$.

Each acceptance threshold is determined by balancing two complementary criteria, based on user-defined parameters, namely, prediction accuracy and exit coverage. The first criterion, accuracy, ensures that accepted predictions are highly reliable. For a given entropy threshold τ_e , the accuracy of accepted samples $A(\tau_e)$ is computed as

$$A(\tau_e) = \frac{C_{CA,e}(\tau_e)}{C_{CA,e}(\tau_e) + C_{WA,e}(\tau_e)}. \quad (8)$$

Here, the subscript e indicates that all counts refer to values at a specific intermediate exit e for the given exit-specific entropy threshold τ_e . Note that in (4) we omitted the subscript e as we only consider the counts at the final exit of the ResNet+R model. We define $\tau_{\alpha,e}$ as the largest threshold for which $A(\tau_e) \geq \alpha$, with α being a predefined accuracy target. The second criterion, coverage, promotes computational efficiency by ensuring that a sufficient number of samples are accepted early. The coverage at an intermediate exit $R(\tau_e)$ is

defined as

$$R(\tau_e) = \frac{C_{CA,e}(\tau_e) + C_{WA,e}(\tau_e)}{C_{CA,e}(\tau_e) + C_{WA,e}(\tau_e) + C_{CR,e}(\tau_e) + C_{WR,e}(\tau_e)}. \quad (9)$$

The coverage threshold $\tau_{\rho,e}$ is defined as the smallest threshold such that $R(\tau_e) \geq \rho$, where ρ is a predefined minimum coverage target. To balance accuracy and coverage, the final acceptance threshold is set as the average of the two bounds expressed as

$$\tau_{\text{accept},e} = \frac{\tau_{\alpha,e} + \tau_{\rho,e}}{2}. \quad (10)$$

Once the threshold is determined and the classifier retrained, the parameters used to obtain the decision at that exit, are frozen before proceeding to the next classifier. The final exit ($e = N_e - 1$) follows a different procedure. After retraining on its respective dataset \mathcal{D}_{N_e-1} , a rejection threshold $\tau_{\text{reject},N_e-1}$ is computed analogously to the rejection mechanism in the selective ResNet model. This threshold partitions the data into confidently accepted samples and a rejected subset $\mathcal{D}_{\text{reject,final}}$, which is passed to the next processing stage. The optimal rejection threshold is chosen to maximize the classification quality metric $Q(\tau)$, as defined in (4). This progressive and structured fine-tuning process ensures that each expert is optimized for the complexity level of the samples it receives, while maintaining a consistent trade-off between prediction confidence and computational efficiency across all exits.

3) REJECTION THRESHOLD DETERMINATION

To further enhance computational efficiency, the intermediate exits are also equipped with rejection thresholds $\tau_{\text{reject},e}$. It is crucial to note that in the WWEE+R implementation, where early rejection is not employed at intermediate stages, these intermediate rejection thresholds are set to a value greater than 1. This ensures that all samples pass through the initial exits without rejection, reserving the selective classification functionality exclusively for the final exit. For the WWEE+ER implementation, the rejection thresholds are designed to identify and discard samples early in the pipeline that are likely to result in incorrect final classifications. The thresholds are derived by analyzing the entropy of predictions on a subset of the training data, denoted $\mathcal{D}_{\text{reject,final}}$, which contains samples that were ultimately rejected at the final exit during the expert-specific fine-tuning. The rejection thresholds are determined sequentially. For the first intermediate exit, we consider the full $\mathcal{D}_{\text{reject,final}}$ and determine $\tau_{\text{reject},0}$ by maximizing the classification quality $Q(\tau)$, as defined in (4). Once this threshold is determined, we partition the dataset based on whether samples would be rejected at this exit, resulting in a subset of remaining samples that are passed on to the next stage. This process is repeated for each subsequent intermediate exit. At each step, we use the data that has neither been accepted nor rejected by earlier exits to compute the next rejection threshold. In this way, we iteratively define

all $N_e - 2$ intermediate rejection thresholds. For the final exit ($N_e - 1$), a separate rejection threshold is not required; its acceptance threshold inherently acts as a binary decision between accepting or rejecting the prediction.

C. INFERENCE PROCEDURE

The inference process for WWEE, presented in Algorithm 2, is a dynamic procedure that adapts the computational effort based on the input sample's characteristics. This is achieved by leveraging the $\tau_{\text{accept},e}$ and $\tau_{\text{reject},e}$ thresholds established during training. When a new sample X is fed into the WWEE network, it is processed through a sequence of branches. At each intermediate exit e , the model evaluates the entropy $H(\hat{y}_e)$ of the predicted probability distribution to determine the appropriate action, namely, confident acceptance, confident rejection, or deferral to a subsequent branch.

- **Confidently Accept:** If $H(\hat{y}_e) < \tau_{\text{accept},e}$, the model considers the prediction highly confident and accepts it as the final output. The prediction is obtained by taking the maximum argument of the probability distribution. The inference process terminates at this point, resulting in reduced computational cost.
- **Confidently Reject:** If $H(\hat{y}_e) \geq \tau_{\text{reject},e}$, the model identifies the prediction as too uncertain to trust. The sample is rejected outright, and no classification output is produced. This avoids wasting further computation on samples unlikely to be correctly classified. The inference process terminates at this point, resulting in reduced computational cost.
- **Defer Decision:** If $\tau_{\text{accept},e} \leq H(\hat{y}_e) < \tau_{\text{reject},e}$, the model defers the classification decision. The sample is passed to the next (wider) branch, where more expressive features can be extracted. The feature maps from the current and previous branches are concatenated to enrich the representation for subsequent classification.

Should a sample traverse all intermediate branches and reach the final exit ($N_e - 1$), the option to defer the decision is no longer available. At this conclusive stage, the final rejection threshold $\tau_{\text{reject},N_e-1}$ solely determines whether the final prediction is outputted or rejected, a behavior consistent with the ResNet+R model

VI. EXPERIMENT SETUP

This section details the experimental setup employed to train our proposed WWEE and ResNet base models, which are then configured into distinct implementations (WWEE+R, WWEE+ER, and ResNet+R) for comprehensive comparison in AMC. We describe the datasets used, the rationale behind the parameter choices for these base models, and the methodology for selecting their best-performing instances. Crucially, these distinct implementations are formed by appropriately applying and determining their respective acceptance and rejection thresholds, detailed in Section VII.

Algorithm 2 WWEE Inference

Require: X Input vector of IQ-samples
 θ trained weights of the model,
 $\tau_{\text{accept},0 \dots N_e-2}$ acceptance thresholds,
 $\tau_{\text{reject},0 \dots N_e-1}$ rejection thresholds.

Ensure: \hat{m} prediction **if** *accepted*, **else** None

- 1: $[X_0, X_1, \dots, X_{N_e-1}] \leftarrow X$ ▷ split input into N_e subvectors
- 2: $[\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_{N_e-1}] \leftarrow \theta$ ▷ Split model into branches
- 3: **for** $e = 0$ to $N_e - 1$ **do**
- 4: $\hat{y} \leftarrow \text{Infer}(X_e, \theta_e)$
- 5: **if** $H(\hat{y}) < \tau_{\text{accept},e}$ **then** ▷ Confidently Accept
- 6: $\hat{m} \leftarrow \arg \max \hat{y}$
- 7: **return** \hat{m}
- 8: **else if** $H(\hat{y}) \geq \tau_{\text{reject},e}$ **then** ▷ Confidently Reject
- 9: **return** None
- 10: **else** ▷ Defer Decision
- 11: // Continue to the next iteration (implicit)
- 12: **end if**
- 13: **end for**

A. DATASETS

We generated two synthetic datasets, one solely for model training and candidate selection, and a second exclusively for evaluating the selected WWEE and ResNet models. Both datasets were created using Python and the GNU Radio software-defined radio toolkit [37] to simulate signal transmission through a flat fading channel with both attenuation and AWGN. For each generated signal, we extracted frames consisting of 512 consecutive IQ samples from a single modulation. This was done with an oversampling rate of two samples per symbol, with a corresponding symbol rate of 1 MSymbol/s. During both training and inference, these samples were segmented in a manner consistent with the input requirements of our proposed WWEE models and the ResNet model. The resulting received signals span a SNR range from -20 dB to 20 dB, with increments of 2 dB. This extensive SNR range allows for a comprehensive evaluation of both considered models under various signal quality conditions, facilitating a fair and thorough comparison. We selected a dataset size of 2048 input frames per modulation SNR pair for both the training and testing datasets to guarantee the statistical significance of our results. This ample number of frames allows for a comprehensive and reliable assessment of the model's performance, mitigating potential biases that could arise from a smaller sample size. The set of modulation schemes strategically chosen for this study is:

$$\mathcal{M} = \{\text{BPSK}, \text{QPSK}, \text{PSK8}, \text{PAM4}, \text{QAM16}, \text{QAM64}\}.$$

While this selection represents a focused subset of digital modulation techniques commonly used and fundamentally related, the increasing complexity within this set, from simple binary modulation to higher-order quadrature amplitude modulation, provides a challenging test scenario, enabling us to evaluate the classifiers' ability to perform fine-grained

modulation classification in the presence of noise. To assess real-world performance and generalizability, we also evaluate our models using the RadioML 2018.01A dataset, a publicly available, over-the-air captured dataset provided by DeepSig Inc. [38]. This dataset is a well-established benchmark in the field. From it, we extracted the six modulation classes corresponding to those in our synthetic dataset. The extracted data includes received SNR values ranging from -20 dB to 30 dB. It is important to note that the final WWEE architecture was optimized exclusively on the synthetic datasets and was not further adjusted or re-optimized for the RadioML dataset. This approach ensures that the evaluation on the RadioML dataset serves as a true test of the model’s generalizability to real-world conditions.

B. MODEL PARAMETERS

Having previously detailed the architecture of our proposed WWEE model and the ResNet model, this subsection focuses on the specific parameter configurations chosen for our experiments. Our primary goal in selecting these parameters was to enable a fair comparison between the two base models, particularly concerning their computational demands during inference.

For the base WWEE model, which incorporates 3 parallel branches, each branch consists of a feature extraction block, followed by a decision block, and an exit block. The feature extraction block in each branch is structured with 4 residual stacks, with each convolutional layer employing 32 filters and a kernel size of (1, 3). The decision block in each branch comprises two dense layers, each containing 128 neurons, followed by the output layer corresponding to the number of modulation classes. This structural design of the individual branches is chosen to provide comparable representational capacity at each processing stage within the WWEE architecture. The WWEE architecture processes an input of 512×2 IQ samples through a series of branches. The key design principle is to ensure the sample size increases significantly with each subsequent branch. This ordered increase, even with small variations, effectively highlights the trade-off between accuracy and computational load. For a prediction at the first exit, only the initial 32×2 samples are considered. This number was selected as it strikes a balance between computational load and classification performance. Pilot experiments demonstrated that this small number of samples is sufficient for accurately classifying signals at higher SNRs, allowing for early exits. The goal of the initial exit is to be as computationally efficient as possible while still achieving a basic level of classification performance. Selecting a larger number of samples would yield higher accuracy for the first exit, but at a greater computational cost, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The second branch then incorporates 160×2 new IQ samples alongside the features extracted by the first branch. Consequently, the decision at the second exit is based on a combined input equivalent to 192×2 IQ samples (32×2 from the first segment and 160×2 new samples) Based on pilot experi-

TABLE 1. Design parameter and properties for the considered models.

Block	Parameters	ResNet	WWEE		
Input block	Input Size	384x2	512x2		
Splitting	Split		32x2	160x2	320x2
Feature Block	ResStacks	4	4	4	4
	Filter Sizes	32	32	32	32
	Kernel Sizes	(1,3)	(1,3)	(1,3)	(1,3)
Decision Block	Dense Layer	128	128	128	128
	Dense Layer	128	128	128	128
Exit Block	Size	6	6	6	6

ments, we observed that a second model of this size yields a sufficient increase in accuracy for the samples that did not exit early. The final exit adds another 320×2 samples, resulting in the final exit predicting on the full 512×2 IQ sample input (cf. Fig. 1).

For the first two intermediate exits, acceptance thresholds are determined by two criteria: a prediction accuracy α of 95% (to ensure high accuracy of accepted predictions) and an exit coverage ρ of 25% (to promote computational efficiency by ensuring at least 25% of inputs are handled at these early exits). This specific input size, splitting strategy, and parameter selection for ρ and α are chosen empirically by pilot experiments, considering the trade-off between early exit usage and the computational load incurred at each exit, ultimately aiming to balance computational efficiency and accuracy during inference. For the ResNet+R model, the architecture can be viewed as a single processing path similar in structure to the individual branches of the WWEE model. The input to the ResNet is a segment of 384×2 IQ samples. This input size is chosen to achieve a comparable average computational cost per inference to the proposed WWEE+R model. The key design parameters for both models are summarized in Table 1.

The computational load, measured in Million FLOPs (MFLOPs) per single input inference, and the number of trainable parameters for the ResNet model and each exit of the WWEE model are presented in Table 2. While the ResNet’s computational load remains constant, the WWEE model’s varies based on its exit point. Notably, the reported parameter counts and MFLOPs for WWEE’s exit points are cumulative. For instance, at exit 1, the cost includes computation up to exit 0 plus the feature extraction and decision block of exit 1. It is important to note that the absolute computational load can be influenced by specific hardware and software implementations. Thus, while MFLOPs serve as a useful metric for comparing inherent computational demands, actual power consumption, inference time, and memory usage (derived from trainable parameters) may vary across platforms.

To assess the memory footprint, storage usage, and latency of the models, we converted them to the TensorFlow Lite format using its built-in tools. We then ran them on a Rasp-

TABLE 2. MFLOPs and amount of trainable parameters for resnet+r model and each exit of the proposed WWEE model.

	MFLOPs	Parameters
ResNet	9.40	169 670
Exit 0	0.80	79 558
Exit 1	4.73	200 076
Exit 2	12.62	402 514

TABLE 3. Latency, memory, and storage for resnet+r model and each exit of the proposed WWEE model on a raspberry pi 4.

	Latency (μs)	Memory (MB)	Storage (MB)
ResNet	1789.81	6.61	1.20
Exit 0	261.02	4.62	0.45
Exit 1	1110.83	6.40	1.01
Exit 2	2700.25	10.31	2.60

berry Pi 4 Model B Rev 1.1 with 2GB of RAM using the TensorFlow Lite benchmark tool. The results are presented in Table 3.

Note that the latency, memory, and storage values for Exit 1 are cumulative, including the computational overhead of Exit 0. Similarly, the values for Exit 2 include the overhead of both Exit 0 and Exit 1, reflecting the sequential processing of the WWEE architecture.

C. CANDIDATE SELECTION

Following the definition of the model parameters and their computational costs, we now describe the training procedure employed for both architectures. We trained 16 copies of each base model (ResNet and WWEE) using different random initial weights. Each copy was trained on a training/selection dataset, randomly split into training (75%), validation (12.5%), and a test set (12.5%), ensuring an equal representation of all SNR-modulation pairs across these splits. To mitigate overfitting, early stopping based on the validation set performance was implemented during each training session, with a maximum of 40 epochs. Crucially, the base ResNet model underwent one training session, while the base WWEE model required four sessions (one joint training and three specialized fine-tuning sessions for each of its exits). From these trained copies, the ResNet model and the WWEE model, each exhibiting the highest overall accuracy on their respective internal test sets, were selected for subsequent analysis and implementation variants. For these selected models, the acceptance and rejection thresholds for their respective configurations were determined during training.

VII. MODEL IMPLEMENTATIONS

Using the optimized thresholds determined during the training procedure, we consider five distinct model implementations for comprehensive comparative analysis:

- **ResNet:** A conventional ResNet model without any selective classification or rejection mechanism. This is

TABLE 4. Optimized acceptance and rejection thresholds for each model implementation. Values of $\tau_{\text{reject}} > 1$ indicate that the rejection mechanism is effectively disabled for that specific exit in the given implementation.

Model Implementation	Exit	τ_{accept}	τ_{reject}
ResNet	Final	/	> 1
ResNet+R	Final	/	0.687
WWEE	Exit 0	0.405	> 1
	Exit 1	0.298	> 1
	Exit 2	/	> 1
WWEE+R	Exit 0	0.405	> 1
	Exit 1	0.298	> 1
	Exit 2	/	0.525
WWEE+ER	Exit 0	0.405	0.987
	Exit 1	0.298	0.882
	Exit 2	/	0.525

achieved by setting its rejection threshold to a value greater than 1.

- **ResNet+R:** The ResNet model augmented with a selective classification mechanism, employing a rejection threshold at its final output layer.
- **WWEE:** A width-wise early exiting model focused solely on computational efficiency through early acceptance. Intermediate exits do not perform rejection.
- **WWEE+R:** The WWEE model extended with a selective classification mechanism, where rejection is performed exclusively at the final output layer, similar to ResNet+R. Intermediate exits do not perform rejection.
- **WWEE+ER:** The full WWEE model, incorporating selective classification with rejection mechanisms at both its intermediate and final exits, maximizing trustworthiness alongside efficiency.

An overview of each model and the corresponding implemented thresholds can be found in Table 4.

VIII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents a comprehensive analysis of the experimental results, evaluating the performance of the proposed WWEE+R and WWEE+ER architecture against the ResNet+R model across various metrics. We delve into the models' classification accuracy, dataset coverage with rejection mechanisms, and computational efficiency, offering insights into their behavior under different SNR conditions and for diverse modulation schemes. In this results section, we primarily focus on the synthetically generated datasets. However, we also present a comparative analysis using the RadioML 2018.01A dataset, a widely recognised benchmark for assessing real-world performance.

A. ACCURACY WITHOUT REJECTION MECHANISM

In this subsection, we present the classification accuracy of the considered base models, that is, where no rejection mechanism is active. Accuracy, defined as the percentage

FIGURE 5. Accuracy performance of models without a rejection mechanism, evaluated across varying SNR levels.

of correctly classified in-distribution samples per SNR level, serves as a fundamental performance metric in the absence of rejection capability. Consequently, the performance of the WWeE+ER at each intermediate branch is identical to that of the WWeE+R in this analysis. These results highlight the inherent classification capabilities of both the proposed WWeE architecture and the base ResNet model when all predictions are accepted.

Fig. 5 illustrates the overall classification accuracies achieved by the considered models across the tested SNR range. As typically observed in modulation classification tasks, performance is lower in noisy environments (low SNR) and progressively improves as the signal strength increases, generally leveling off beyond 10 dB SNR. Notably, the models exhibit similar accuracy levels in the challenging low-SNR regime (up to 0 dB). However, at higher SNR values, the WWeE architecture demonstrates a clear advantage, surpassing the performance of the ResNet model. Examining the peak performance, the WWeE model reaches a slightly higher maximum accuracy of 89.2% compared to the ResNet model's 87.5%. From an application perspective in AMC, this difference is often considered negligible. Considering the average performance across all SNRs, the WWeE model achieves 57.3% accuracy, a marginal improvement over the ResNet's 56.4%, indicating generally similar overall behavior in terms of classification accuracy.

A more in-depth analysis of the classification accuracy, broken down by individual modulation scheme and SNR, is visualized in Fig. 6. This heatmap displays the difference in accuracy between the WWeE model and the ResNet model, with red indicating an improvement by the WWeE model and blue indicating superior performance by the ResNet. The overall slight advantage in global accuracy observed for the WWeE model at higher SNRs can be largely attributed to its enhanced ability to correctly classify QAM64. In the mid-SNR region, the WWeE model demonstrates a notable strength in classifying PSK8, achieving a maximum accuracy

FIGURE 6. Heatmap of accuracy difference: Proposed WWeE model versus ResNet model per modulation and SNR. The heatmap colors represent the percentage difference in accuracy between the classifiers' results. Red indicates higher accuracy for the proposed WWeE model, while blue indicates higher accuracy for the ResNet model.

difference of 23% at 2 dB SNR compared to the ResNet. Conversely, the ResNet model shows better performance around 4 dB SNR, with approximately 10% higher accuracy for BPSK and around 14% higher accuracy for PAM4 at 2 dB SNR. In the challenging low-SNR regime, the WWeE model exhibits a relative advantage of around 5% in classifying QPSK and PSK8 compared to the ResNet.

Fig. 7 shows the confusion matrices for both the ResNet and WWeE models, aggregated across the full SNR range of -20 to 20 dB. The overall performance of both models is similar. The diagonal elements of the matrices show the classification accuracy for each modulation scheme. BPSK and PAM4 are classified with the highest accuracy, while QAM16 and QAM64 have the lowest. This indicates that modulation schemes with a higher number of bits per symbol are more difficult to classify accurately across varying signal quality conditions.

The primary classification errors occur between modulation schemes with similar characteristics. For instance, both models frequently confuse BPSK and PAM4 with each other. A more significant confusion is observed between the higher-order modulation schemes, QAM16 and QAM64, which are often misclassified as one another.

In summary, while both models exhibit comparable overall classification accuracy in the absence of a rejection mechanism, the detailed per-modulation analysis reveals distinct strengths and weaknesses for specific modulation schemes and SNR regions, suggesting nuanced differences in their classification behaviour.

B. DATASET COVERAGE WITH REJECTION MECHANISM

This subsection analyzes the dataset coverage, defined as the percentage of samples accepted (i.e., not rejected) by each of the three considered models ResNet+R, WWeE+R, and WWeE+ER when their respective rejection mechanisms are active. It is important to note the distinction in their rejection mechanisms. For the ResNet+R and WWeE+R models, rejection occurs exclusively at the final output, whereas the WWeE+ER model also employs rejection at its earlier intermediate exits. Understanding the dataset coverage, in conjunction with the classification quality discussed previ-

(a) ResNet

(b) WVEE

FIGURE 7. Confusion matrices for both the ResNet and WVEE models. Each cell shows the percentage of samples from the true modulation scheme (y-axis) that were classified as a predicted modulation scheme (x-axis). The models were evaluated across a range of SNR levels.

ously, provides valuable insights into the models' behaviour and their trade-off between accuracy and the willingness to abstain from making predictions. While maintaining good overall dataset coverage is generally important, a more aggressive rejection strategy, as seen in the WVEE+ER model, could also be viewed as a form of specialization, prioritizing high-confidence predictions in specific operational environments.

Fig. 8 illustrates the dataset coverage for the ResNet+R, WVEE+R, and WVEE+ER models across the tested SNR range. A clear trend of increasing coverage with increasing SNR is observed for all models. At SNRs above 8 dB, all models accept nearly all samples. Conversely, below -16 dB, almost all samples are rejected, highlighting a fundamental SNR limitation inherent to the base ResNet architecture. The most notable differences in dataset coverage between the models become apparent in the SNR region between -12 dB and 0 dB, where both the ResNet+R and the WVEE+R models consistently exhibit higher acceptance rates compared to the WVEE+ER model.

FIGURE 8. Dataset coverage of models with rejection mechanisms, evaluated across varying SNR levels.

FIGURE 9. Modulation-specific dataset coverage for models with rejection mechanisms, averaged across all SNR levels.

This observed difference, particularly the lower acceptance rates of WVEE+ER, is attributed to its more aggressive early rejection strategy. This strategy significantly reduces the number of samples that propagate through the entire model. For instance, the WVEE+ER model rejects 43.93% of all input samples exclusively at its final exit. In contrast, the WVEE+R model is designed for earlier decisions: it rejects 17.53% of samples at the first intermediate exit and an additional 17.16% at the second intermediate exit. Consequently, only 12.50% of all samples reach and are rejected at its final exit. This distributed, proactive rejection results in a total rejection rate of 47.19% for WVEE+ER across all stages. Comparing the models, the average acceptance rates across the entire SNR range are 56.04% for the WVEE+R model, 54.85% for the ResNet+R model, and 52.81% for the WVEE+ER model.

Fig. 9 presents the dataset coverage per modulation scheme, averaged across all tested SNRs. The WVEE+ER model consistently exhibits a lower coverage (at least 1% less) compared to the ResNet+R and WVEE+R models.

Notably, all models show a significantly higher acceptance rate for BPSK and PAM4 (around 20% more) compared to the other, more complex modulation types. When comparing the models' performance on BPSK and PAM4, we observe that the WWEE+ER model rejects around 8% more samples than the WWEE+R model. As previously noted in the general result, this stems from the early rejection mechanism in WWEE+ER. It proactively discards samples from these modulations that the later exits in the WWEE+R model might otherwise have accepted. The higher acceptance rates for BPSK and PAM4 across all models stem from their inherent low complexity, making them easier to classify even at lower SNRs, thus reducing uncertainty and the need for rejection.

Whereas the WWEE+ER model exhibits the lowest dataset coverage among the evaluated models, this difference is comparatively small: 3.23% lower than WWEE+R and 2.04% lower than ResNet+R. This minimal impact on dataset coverage underscores the WWEE+ER model's ability to intelligently filter out lower-confidence predictions without severely limiting its operational scope. This proactive rejection strategy is a deliberate design choice that significantly enhances the classification quality of the accepted samples. By mitigating false positives, the WWEE+ER model becomes inherently more trustworthy, a crucial advantage in operational environments where precision and reliability are important. Ultimately, this demonstrates the model's capability to balance computational efficiency with robust, high-confidence decision-making.

C. INFLUENCE OF EARLY REJECTION ON CLASSIFICATION QUALITY

Here, we examine the classification quality of the considered models, as defined in (4). It is important to note that this analysis incorporates the rejection mechanism, including both early rejection and rejection at the final exit. Furthermore, the classification quality without any rejection mechanism is equivalent to the accuracy presented in the previous section. This metric provides a score indicating the trustworthiness of the model's actions in different environments, rewarding both correct predictions and the rejection of incorrect samples. A high classification quality score suggests high confidence in the model's decisions, while a low score indicates uncertainty. By analyzing the classification quality in detail, we can identify the model with the highest confidence for a given environment.

Fig. 10a illustrates the classification quality of the ResNet+R, WWEE+R, and WWEE+ER models across the tested SNR range next to the classification accuracy of the base ResNet and base WWEE models. All three models achieve relatively high classification quality at both low and high SNRs, with lower scores observed in the intermediate SNR region. This mid-SNR dip occurs because these mid-SNR levels represent the most challenging classification scenarios. The signals are not so clear as to be easily classified with high confidence (leading to acceptance), nor are they so noisy as to be clearly rejected with high

confidence. Consequently, the decision boundary between accepting and rejecting becomes more ambiguous, resulting in a higher number of misclassifications. For SNRs below 0 dB, the WWEE+ER model achieves higher classification quality, outperforming ResNet+R by approximately 3.3% and WWEE+R by approximately 3.1%. This improved performance is directly attributable to the strategically correct rejection of samples at the intermediate exits where the early rejection mechanism is active. By abstaining from low-confidence predictions, the WWEE+ER model effectively mitigates the negative impact of misclassifications on its overall classification quality score. Interestingly, for SNRs above 0 dB, the behavior of the WWEE and WWEE+ER models becomes virtually identical in terms of classification quality. In this high-SNR regime, the classification quality is primarily dictated by the early acceptance of high-confidence samples, rather than by rejection, as most samples are easily classified. The average classification quality scores are 0.784 for the ResNet+R model, 0.79 for the WWEE+R model, and 0.807 for the WWEE+ER model, indicating generally similar overall trustworthiness based on this metric. A similar analysis was conducted on the RadioML 2018.01A dataset, with the results illustrated in Fig. 10b. The trends observed on this real-world dataset closely mirror those of the synthetic data. At low SNRs, the WWEE+ER model maintains a higher classification quality compared to the other models, demonstrating its superior performance in challenging, low-signal conditions. All models exhibit a noticeable dip in classification quality around 0 dB, confirming that this remains a particularly ambiguous region regardless of the dataset. For SNRs above 0 dB, all models converge in performance, as the high signal quality simplifies the classification task and reduces the need for the rejection mechanism. These findings on the RadioML dataset confirm the generalizability of our observations and demonstrate that the benefits of the WWEE+ER approach are not limited to our synthetic data.

Fig. 12 presents a detailed breakdown of the classification quality for each individual modulation scheme at three specific SNR values: -10 dB (low), 0 dB (mid), and 10 dB (high). At a low SNR of -10 dB, Fig. 11a shows that the WWEE+ER model outperforms the other two models for BPSK and PAM4. For the remaining modulations, performance across all models is comparable. The improved classification quality for BPSK and PAM4 in the WWEE+ER model is attributed to its more conservative decision-making strategy, which prioritizes rejecting low-confidence samples, thereby preventing incorrect classifications. Generally, all models exhibit higher classification quality for PSK8, QAM16, and QAM64 at this low SNR. This is likely due to the inherent difficulty in distinguishing these complex modulations from noise, leading to a higher rate of correct rejections. At an SNR of 0 dB, Fig. 11b indicates that the classification quality scores for BPSK and PAM4 are relatively high across all models, whereas scores for other modulations remain lower. Interestingly, the ResNet+R model shows a surprising increase in classification quality for

FIGURE 10. Classification quality of models with and without rejection mechanisms on both the synthetic and RadioML 2018.01A datasets, evaluated across various SNR levels.

FIGURE 11. Modulation-specific classification quality across representative SNR conditions: low (a), medium (b), and high (c) for the synthetic datasets.

BPSK and PAM4 at this SNR. This phenomenon potentially arises because the WWEE+R and WWEE+ER models tend to make decisions at earlier, less complex network exits compared to the full architecture utilized by the ResNet+R model. The ResNet+R model’s consistent use of its full complexity might offer an advantage for these specific modulation-SNR combinations. However, while the ResNet+R model shows better performance for BPSK and PAM4 at 0 dB, it generally underperforms compared to the WWEE and WWEE+ER models for QPSK and PSK8. The overall average classification quality across all modulations at 0 dB remains relatively close between the three models. Finally, at a high SNR of 10 dB, Fig. 11c illustrates that while classification scores approach 1 for all classifications, we observe a consistently lower classification quality score for QAM16 and QAM64 across all three models. This is likely due to the inherent complexity of these higher-order modulations. In particular, there is a noticeable difference between the ResNet+R model and the WWEE+R and WWEE+ER models for QAM64, with the ResNet+R model exhibiting approximately 20% lower classification quality.

D. INFLUENCE OF EARLY REJECTION ON COMPUTATIONAL EFFICIENCY

The computational efficiency of a model is a critical consideration for practical deployment, directly impacting energy consumption and inference latency. This section presents an analysis of the computational load for the ResNet+R, WWEE+R, and WWEE+ER models, quantified by the average number of MFLOPs required per inference across the tested SNR range. It is important to note that while the number of MFLOPs for an individual sample’s prediction depends solely on the exit taken, samples within the same group (defined by SNR and modulation) can exit at different exits. Consequently, the reported average load reflects the distribution of samples across these various exits, rather than the fixed computational cost of any single exit.

Fig. 12a illustrates the average computational load for each model as a function of SNR. As anticipated, the ResNet+R model exhibits a constant computational load of 9.4 MFLOPs, independent of the input SNR. This reflects its fixed processing path for all samples. In contrast, the WWEE+R and WWEE+ER models demonstrate

FIGURE 12. Computational load of models with rejection mechanisms, evaluated across varying SNR levels.

SNR-dependent computational loads. Notably, the computational demand for both models decreases with increasing SNR, indicating that easier-to-classify samples require less computation. Above 8 dB SNR, the computational load of the WWEE+R and WWEE+ER models converges, as the observed computational efficiency in this range is primarily driven by the early acceptance of samples. For low SNRs, WWEE+ER exhibits a significantly lower computational load compared to the WWEE+R model. Furthermore, the computational load of WWEE+ER reduces with decreasing SNR, while the opposite is true for the WWEE+R model, which plateaus at 12.62 MFLOPs below -8 dB SNR. This suggests that under very noisy conditions, the earlier exits in the WWEE+R model are not effectively utilized.

The overall average computational load for the WWEE+R model (9.04 MFLOPs) is comparable to the ResNet+R model. The WWEE+ER model achieves the lowest average computational load of 5.64 MFLOPs, representing a reduction of approximately 40% compared to the ResNet+R model and the WWEE+R model. This efficiency is attributed to its adaptive processing strategy, that is low-SNR samples, deemed challenging, are rejected early, while high-SNR samples are typically accepted at earlier, less computationally intensive exits. The highest computational load for the WWEE+ER model is observed in the mid-SNR range, where the decision to accept or reject is more complex due to the more ambiguous decision boundary between accepting and rejecting. This dynamic computational resource allocation shown in WWEE+ER highlights the promising potential of combining early exiting with early rejection for significant gains in computational efficiency. A similar analysis of computational load was performed on the RadioML 2018.01A dataset, with the results displayed in Fig. 12b. The trends observed on this real-world dataset are consistent with those from the synthetic data. As the WWEE+ER model's architecture was not re-optimized for this dataset, its adaptive strategy leads to a more pronounced rejection of samples

FIGURE 13. Heatmap of computational load difference: Proposed WWEE+R model versus ResNet+R model per modulation and SNR. The heatmap colors represent the difference in computational load (in MFLOPs) between the two models. Blue indicates a lower computational load for the proposed WWEE+R model, while red indicates a lower computational load for the ResNet+R model.

where it is less confident, particularly at lower SNRs. This conservative behavior results in a significant reduction in computational load for challenging, low-SNR examples. Consequently, the overall average computational load for the WWEE+ER model on the RadioML dataset is remarkably low at 2.97 MFLOPs. This represents a substantial efficiency gain compared to the WWEE+R model (8.65 MFLOPs) and the ResNet+R model (9.40 MFLOPs). This result powerfully demonstrates that the promising reductions in computational load offered by the WWEE+ER approach are not dependent on a dataset-specific architectural fine-tuning, highlighting the generalizability of its efficiency gains.

Since the computational load of the ResNet+R model remains constant across all SNR levels and modulation schemes, in the following, we analyze the relative computational efficiency of the WWEE+R and WWEE+ER models by examining the differential heatmaps with respect to ResNet+R presented in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14. In these figures, blue regions indicate where the WWEE+R or WWEE+ER model exhibits a lower computational load (i.e., outperforms

FIGURE 14. Heatmap of computational load difference: Proposed WWEE+ER model versus ResNet+R model per modulation and SNR. The heatmap colors represent the difference in computational load (in MFLOPs) between the two models. Blue indicates a lower computational load for the proposed WWEE+ER model, while red indicates a lower computational load for the ResNet+R model.

the ResNet+R in efficiency), while red regions signify a higher computational load compared to the ResNet+R.

Analyzing the WWEE+R model’s differential computational load, as shown in Fig. 13, we observe that computational gains at higher SNRs primarily stem from the early acceptance of BPSK, QPSK, PSK8, and PAM4 samples. Conversely, the computational load per sample for QAM16 and QAM64 is generally higher than that of the ResNet+R model across most SNR levels. However, this increased computational cost for more complex modulations, particularly QAM64, correlates with a corresponding improvement in classification quality at higher SNRs, as depicted in Fig. 11c.

Examining the differential computational load of the WWEE+ER model in Fig. 14, we observe a similar trend of reduced computational load at higher SNRs, with the exception of QAM16 and QAM64. More notably, at lower SNRs, the WWEE+ER model consistently demonstrates a lower computational load across all modulation schemes. This highlights the effectiveness of the early rejection mechanism in specifically targeting and discarding more challenging samples early in the processing pipeline, thereby leading to significant computational savings.

Overall, the WWEE+ER model offers the most computationally efficient operation compared to the other models, making it particularly attractive for deployment on resource-constrained edge devices. However, as discussed in the previous section, this computational advantage comes with a trade-off in terms of dataset coverage due to the early rejection strategy.

IX. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the performance of a novel WWEE architecture, both without and with an early rejection mechanism (WWEE+R and WWEE+ER), in comparison to a selective ResNet (ResNet+R) for modulation classification. Our analysis focused on classification quality as a measure of trustworthiness and computational efficiency during inference, complemented by insights from dataset coverage and accuracy. The WWEE+ER model proved to be a superior solution, demonstrating significantly higher classification quality in challenging low-SNR

environments by strategically rejecting low-confidence samples. It achieved an enhanced classification quality of 3% in low-SNR scenarios, notably boosting trustworthiness, while simultaneously reducing the computational load by an average of 40%. This makes WWEE+ER highly attractive for resource-constrained edge devices. Although the ResNet+R model exhibited specific advantages for certain modulation-SNR combinations, and the WWEE+R model invested computational resources for complex modulations, the WWEE+ER consistently delivered an optimized balance of confidence and efficiency. In essence, integrating early rejection into a WWEE+R architecture offers a robust framework for balancing computational efficiency and trustworthiness, paving the way for more intelligent and resource-aware communication systems.

X. FUTURE WORK

The proposed integration of WWEE and early rejection mechanisms has demonstrated significant benefits in achieving computationally efficient and trustworthy AMC. Looking ahead, there are several promising avenues for extending this research. One key direction involves exploring the efficacy of our approach in different application domains within wireless communications, such as channel estimation or interference detection, leveraging AMC as an excellent initial use case.

A crucial next step will be to systematically explore the design space of the WWEE architecture. This paper served as a proof-of-concept; however, the current model’s segmentation ratios were determined empirically. To move toward a more optimized solution, we plan to investigate the impact of different numbers of branches and their corresponding segmentation sizes on model performance and computational load. We also plan to conduct a direct comparative analysis between WWEE and other well-known early-exit strategies, such as BranchyNet, to provide a comprehensive evaluation of our approach’s advantages in computational efficiency and accuracy.

Furthermore, we plan to explore the combined effects of WWEE with other optimization techniques, such as model pruning or knowledge distillation, to demonstrate its potential for even greater gains in practical deployment. Furthermore, this paper primarily focused on evaluating the computational load and trustworthiness of the model at inference. An important next step will be to conduct a detailed analysis of inference time. While reduced computational load generally translates to faster inference, a dedicated study quantifying the real-world latency improvements on various edge hardware platforms could provide interesting insights for practical deployment. This would involve benchmarking the model’s speed across different hardware configurations and under varying signal conditions.

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